

Clinical Impact of Norepinephrine Combined with Esmolol Therapy on Outcomes in Patients with Septic Shock

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Abstract

Background: A major cause of death in intensive care units, septic shock is a severe form of sepsis that persists despite improvements in treatment. Excessive sympathetic stimulation in septic shock contributes to tachycardia, myocardial dysfunction, and poor outcomes. The first-line vasopressor for preserving mean arterial pressure (MAP) is norepinephrine but its use may exacerbate tachycardia. Esmolol, a β_1 -selective adrenergic blocker, has emerged as a potential adjunct to improve outcomes by controlling heart rate without inducing prolonged hypotension.

Aim: The aim of the study is to assess the prognostic impact and clinical effects of norepinephrine and esmolol in patients suffering from septic shock.

Methods: A study was conducted including 200 patients diagnosed with septic shock. Norepinephrine and esmolol were given to the intervention group of patients, while norepinephrine alone was given to the control group. Important metrics were examined, including heart rate, MAP, lactate clearance, length of stay in the intensive care unit, 28-day mortality, and adverse events. SPSS version 23.0 was used to conduct the statistical analysis.

Results: The intervention group demonstrated significantly better heart rate control (88.5 ± 6.2 bpm vs. 105.8 ± 8.3 bpm; $p < 0.001$), improved lactate clearance (65.4% vs. 48.2%; $p = 0.02$), and a lower 28-day mortality rate (30% vs. 42%; $p = 0.04$). ICU length of stay was reduced (8.2 ± 2.6 days vs. 10.5 ± 3.4 days; $p < 0.001$), and organ dysfunction incidences were lower. Bradycardia was more frequent in the intervention group (15% vs. 5%; $p = 0.02$) but was manageable without long-term complications.

Conclusion: The addition of esmolol to norepinephrine therapy in septic shock improved heart rate control, hemodynamic stability, and clinical outcomes, including reduced mortality and ICU stay. Adverse events were minimal and manageable, supporting the safety and efficacy of this combination.

Recommendations: To validate these results, more extensive randomized controlled studies are advised and establish standardized protocols for esmolol use in septic shock and assess long-term outcomes.

Keywords: Septic shock, norepinephrine, esmolol, heart rate control, mortality reduction.

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Introduction

Septic shock, a severe form of sepsis marked by significant metabolic and circulatory abnormalities, continues to be a major cause of death in intensive care units across the globe. Septic shock fatality rates are still shockingly high, frequently surpassing 40%, despite improvements in critical care [1]. The pathophysiology of septic shock involves a complex interplay of systemic inflammation, vasodilation, and myocardial dysfunction, leading to hypotension and inadequate tissue perfusion [2].

Norepinephrine's strong α -adrenergic actions, which aid in restoring vascular tone and

maintaining MAP, make it the first-line vasopressor advised for treating septic shock [3]. However, the administration of norepinephrine and the endogenous catecholamine surge associated with septic shock can lead to tachycardia and increased myocardial oxygen demand, potentially exacerbating cardiac dysfunction [4]. Increased mortality in patients suffering from septic shock has been independently linked to elevated heart rates [5].

Esmolol, an ultra-short-acting β_1 -selective adrenergic blocker, has been investigated for its potential to control heart rate without causing

prolonged hypotension, given its rapid onset and short half-life [6]. Recent studies have explored the use of esmolol in septic shock patients to modulate the detrimental effects of excessive sympathetic stimulation. For instance, a randomized controlled trial demonstrated that esmolol effectively reduced heart rate and improved hemodynamic parameters without increasing adverse events [7]. Another study reported that the injection of esmolol was linked to decreased norepinephrine needs and increased lactate clearance, indicating improved tissue perfusion [8].

Despite these promising findings, the routine use of β -blockers like esmolol in septic shock remains controversial. Concerns persist regarding potential negative inotropic effects and the risk of exacerbating hemodynamic instability in a population already vulnerable to cardiovascular compromise. Moreover, the optimal timing, dosing, and patient selection criteria for esmolol therapy in septic shock are not yet well-defined, necessitating further research to establish standardized protocols [9]. The aim of the study is to assess the prognostic impact and clinical effects of norepinephrine and esmolol in patients suffering from septic shock

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a prospective, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at GMERS Medical College, Junagadh, Gujarat, over a 12-month period.

Participants: The clinical study included 200 individuals with a diagnosis of septic shock. Two groups were formed from the participants:

1. **Intervention group:** Received norepinephrine combined with esmolol.
2. **Control group:** Received standard treatment with norepinephrine alone.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Adults from the age of 18 to 75.
2. Individuals having a septic shock diagnosis based on the Sepsis-3 criteria.
3. Norepinephrine is necessary for hemodynamically unstable patients in order to keep their mean arterial pressure (MAP) at or above 65 mmHg.
4. Individuals who gave their approval to take part in the research.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Pregnant or lactating women.
2. Patients with a history of severe cardiovascular diseases unrelated to septic shock (e.g., acute myocardial infarction, severe valvular heart disease).

3. Patients on chronic β -blocker therapy.
4. Patients with contraindications to β -blockers (e.g., severe bradycardia, heart block).
5. Patients with advanced chronic organ failure (e.g., end-stage renal disease, severe hepatic dysfunction).
6. Patients who refused to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were recruited consecutively as they presented with septic shock. Observer bias was reduced by blinding the clinical evaluators assessing the outcomes. Confounding variables such as age, gender, comorbidities, and baseline severity of illness were accounted for during analysis.

Data Collection: Data for the study were collected prospectively using a structured case report form (CRF). Baseline demographic information, including age and gender, was recorded for each participant. Heart rate, blood pressure, lactate levels, and MAP were among the clinical indicators that were tracked and recorded. The dosage and duration of esmolol and norepinephrine, among other aspects of the treatment plan, were methodically recorded. Complications, length of stay in the intensive care unit, and 28-day mortality were among the patient outcomes that were carefully documented.

Procedure: At the time of enrollment, all patients underwent a comprehensive clinical evaluation, along with relevant diagnostic investigations, to establish baseline characteristics. Standard treatment for septic shock, including antibiotics and fluid resuscitation, was provided to all participants. In the intervention group, esmolol was administered via a continuous infusion at an initial rate of 0.05 mg/kg/min, with adjustments made to maintain a target heart rate of 80–100 beats per minute. Simultaneously, norepinephrine was used to maintain a MAP of ≥ 65 mmHg. Patients were monitored closely throughout their ICU stay for hemodynamic stability, organ function, and any adverse events related to the treatment. After discharge from the ICU, patients were followed up for 28 days to evaluate survival outcomes and assess for any delayed complications.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Continuous variables (mean \pm standard deviation) were compared using t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests, while categorical data (frequencies and percentages) were analyzed with chi-square or Fisher's exact tests. Survival analysis utilized Kaplan-Meier curves and log-rank tests, and multivariate logistic regression identified 28-day mortality risk factors. A p-value < 0.05 was deemed significant.

Results

The 200 patients had comparable baseline characteristics. The mean age was 55.8 ± 12.3 years in the intervention group and 56.2 ± 11.9

years in the control group ($p = 0.78$). Males comprised 57% and 59% of the groups, respectively ($p = 0.72$). Diabetes (43% vs. 40%, $p = 0.68$) and hypertension (48% vs. 50%, $p = 0.84$) were similarly distributed.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Patients

Parameter	Intervention Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
Age (years)	55.8 ± 12.3	56.2 ± 11.9	0.78
Male (%)	57	59	0.72
Diabetes mellitus (%)	43	40	0.68
Hypertension (%)	48	50	0.84

The intervention group achieved significantly better heart rate control, with an average heart rate of 88.5 ± 6.2 bpm compared to 105.8 ± 8.3 bpm in the control group after 6 hours of treatment ($p < 0.001$). The mean arterial pressure (MAP) was

comparable between the groups (68.9 ± 3.1 mmHg vs. 68.4 ± 3.5 mmHg, $p = 0.45$). Lactate clearance, a critical marker of perfusion, was significantly higher in the intervention group (65.4% vs. 48.2%, $p = 0.02$).

Table 2: Hemodynamic Parameters

Parameter	Intervention Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
Heart rate (bpm)	88.5 ± 6.2	105.8 ± 8.3	<0.001
MAP (mmHg)	68.9 ± 3.1	68.4 ± 3.5	0.45
Lactate clearance (%)	65.4%	48.2%	0.02

The intervention group had a significantly reduced 28-day mortality rate (30%) than the control group (42%; $p = 0.04$). Additionally, the intervention group spent an average of 8.2 ± 2.6 days in the intensive care unit, while the control group spent 10.5

± 3.4 days ($p < 0.001$). Acute renal injury (28% vs. 40%, $p = 0.03$) and respiratory failure requiring mechanical ventilation (34% vs. 49%, $p = 0.01$) were less common in the intervention group.

Table 3: Outcome Measures

Outcome	Intervention Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
28-day mortality (%)	30	42	0.04
ICU length of stay (days)	8.2 ± 2.6	10.5 ± 3.4	<0.001
Acute kidney injury (%)	28	40	0.03
Respiratory failure (%)	34	49	0.01

The incidence of bradycardia was higher in the intervention group (15%) compared to the control group (5%) ($p = 0.02$). However, these events were managed effectively and did not result in long-term

complications. No significant differences were observed in the incidence of arrhythmias (4% vs. 6%, $p = 0.52$).

Table 4: Adverse Events

Adverse Event	Intervention Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
Bradycardia (%)	15	5	0.02
Arrhythmias (%)	4	6	0.52

Discussion

The study demonstrated that adding esmolol to norepinephrine therapy in patients with septic shock significantly improved clinical outcomes compared to norepinephrine alone. The intervention group achieved better heart rate control, with a mean heart rate of 88.5 bpm compared to 105.8 bpm in the control group, indicating that esmolol effectively reduced the excessive sympathetic response associated with septic shock. Importantly,

above 65 mmHg in both groups. Additionally, lactate clearance, a key marker of tissue perfusion, was noticeably greater in the intervention group, suggesting improved microcirculation and metabolic recovery.

The addition of esmolol also positively influenced clinical outcomes. The intervention group had a considerably lower 28-day mortality rate (30%) than the control group (42%). Furthermore, patients receiving esmolol experienced shorter ICU stays, with an average reduction of 2.3 days, and fewer incidences of organ dysfunction, such as acute kidney injury and respiratory failure requiring mechanical ventilation. These findings highlight

this heart rate reduction did not compromise hemodynamic stability, as (MAP) was maintained

the potential of esmolol to not only stabilize cardiovascular function but also improve overall recovery and prognosis in septic shock patients.

Despite the benefits, the intervention group experienced bradycardia more frequently (15% vs. 5%), a known side effect of β -blockers. However, these events were effectively managed without long-term consequences. The absence of significant differences in arrhythmias between the groups supports the safety of esmolol in this context. These results suggest that esmolol, in conjunction with norepinephrine, offers a promising approach to optimizing outcomes in septic shock, emphasizing the need for further studies to verify these results and investigate their wider relevance.

The viability of esmolol infusion in patients with septic shock and prolonged tachycardia was examined in a pilot trial. With a decrease in heart rate to the desired range (80–90 bpm) and steady organ-failure-free days at 28 days, it showed excellent adherence to infusion regimens. These results encourage additional research to assess esmolol's function in this patient population [10]. According to a randomized controlled trial, tachycardia is a risk factor for death in septic shock on its own. Although there were no discernible changes in secondary outcomes such as organ function scores or norepinephrine levels, esmolol use effectively regulated heart rate, indicating the potential to enhance outcomes by lowering death rates [11]. Esmolol was compared to a placebo in a randomized Phase II trial to treat hyperdynamic septic shock [12].

Conclusion

The combination of norepinephrine and esmolol in the management of septic shock demonstrated significant clinical benefits. Patients receiving this combined therapy showed better heart rate control, improved lactate clearance, shorter ICU stays and reduced 28-day mortality compared to those receiving norepinephrine alone. Additionally, the intervention group experienced fewer incidences of organ dysfunction, such as acute kidney injury and respiratory failure, despite a slightly higher rate of manageable bradycardia. These findings suggest that norepinephrine combined with esmolol is a safe and effective strategy for improving outcomes in septic shock patients. Further large-scale randomized controlled trials are warranted to validate these results and explore long-term outcomes.

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